

The Persistent Misalignment Between Equity Goals and Educational Outcomes: A Critical Analysis of the Better and Fairer Schools Agreement 2025-2034 (2024)

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Abstract

This thesis investigates the misalignment between the equity goals of the Alice Springs (Mparntwe) Education Declaration (2019) and educational outcomes in Australia, focusing on school funding and regulation. It examines the 2024 Better and Fairer Schools Agreement 2025-2034 (BFSA), a framework aimed at operationalising these equity principles. While the BFSA prioritises needs-based funding through mechanisms like the Schooling Resource Standard (SRS), its narrow focus on financial levers and aspirational accountabilities overlooks deeper structural, cultural, and operational barriers perpetuating systemic inequities.

Using Carol Bacchi's (2009) "What's the Problem Represented to Be?" (WPR) framework, this research analyses how the BFSA's framing of inequity as a funding issue shapes policy priorities, silences alternatives, and produces unintended consequences. The analysis draws on primary policy documents, including the BFSA and parliamentary inquiries, alongside secondary sources like academic research and advocacy reports.

Findings reveal that the BFSA's reliance on voluntary compliance by states and its focus on funding inputs and attainment targets fail to address systemic barriers, such as socio-economic segregation and cultural exclusion. These limitations undermine its capacity to deliver equitable outcomes. The thesis concludes by advocating for stronger accountability, systemic reforms, and a thorough commitment to equity that aligns with the Mparntwe Declaration's vision of excellence and inclusion.

Research Question: *What are the key characteristics of the Australian school funding and regulatory environment, and how do these characteristics contribute to the persistent misalignment between the equity goals articulated in the Alice Springs (Mparntwe) Education Declaration and the realities of educational outcomes?*

Introduction

In Australia, the Mparntwe Declaration (2019) articulates a vision of educational equity and excellence, aiming to ensure that all young Australians, regardless of their background, have access to high-quality and inclusive schooling. However, despite this commitment, persistent inequities remain. These disparities raise critical questions about the alignment between the equity goals outlined in national education policy and the realities of the Australian school funding and regulatory environment.

At the heart of this misalignment is the Better and Fairer Schools Agreement 2025-2034 (hereafter referred to as BFSA), the latest policy framework intended to operationalise the equity principles enshrined in the Mparntwe Declaration. While the BFSA prioritises needs-based funding and resource redistribution through mechanisms such as the Schooling Resource Standard (SRS), its narrow focus on financial inputs and aspirational attainment targets fails to address deeper structural, cultural, and operational barriers that perpetuate systemic inequities. Moreover, the agreement's reliance on voluntary compliance by states and territories, coupled with ambit timelines and accountability mechanisms, undermines its capacity to deliver meaningful and sustained reforms.

This thesis critically examines the BFSA using Carol Bacchi's (2009) "What's the Problem Represented to be?" (WPR) framework. It explores how the policy's framing of educational inequity as predominantly a funding issue shapes its priorities, silences alternative approaches, and produces unintended consequences. By interrogating the key characteristics of the Australian school funding and regulatory environment, this research aims to identify pathways for more comprehensive reforms that align with the equity and excellence goals of the Mparntwe Declaration (2019). In doing so, it contributes to the ongoing policy dialogue on achieving genuine educational equity in Australia.

Literature Review

In this chapter, I review the literature to examine foundational concepts within this thesis, highlight gaps in the literature, and identify areas where my study can contribute. This chapter provides a historical overview of Australian school funding, tracing its evolution to the current federal-state dynamic. It then moves into the complexities of contemporary education policy in Australia, exploring the tensions inherent in the dual governance structure and the influence of neoliberal ideologies on policy agendas. The chapter then examines the Mparntwe Declaration, focusing on its equity goals and their translation into specific policy objectives. It analyses needs-based funding and the SRS, including its challenges and political debates. Following this, the chapter explores the empirical realities of education inequity in Australia, focusing on the relationship between equity and performance. Finally, it examines the policy intent as laid out in the Better Fairer Schools Funding Agreement 2025-2034, aimed at achieving greater equity and alignment with the Mparntwe Declaration's goals. This literature review provides a foundation for understanding the complexities of Australian school funding, regulation, and their impact on equity outcomes, setting the stage for the subsequent analysis presented in this thesis.

Background: brief history of school funding in Australia

Australian school funding and regulation have a complex history rooted in its federal structure. Initially, education was a state responsibility, with the 1870s-1880s establishing free, compulsory, and non-denominational elementary schools. This led to the Catholic Church establishing its parallel system, receiving no public funding (Gurr, 2020), with the Commonwealth's role limited until the mid-20th century. The 1960s marked a turning point with the introduction of "state aid" to private schools, driven by political considerations and evolving social dynamics (Eacott, 2024). The Whitlam government in the 1970s further systematised Commonwealth funding, leading to the landmark Karmel Report (Karmel, 1973), which laid the foundation for ongoing public funding of private schools. This established a 'concurrent federalism' model (Lingard, 2000), with overlapping responsibilities for state, territory and commonwealth governments. However, the system has in reality maintained a 'coordinate federalism' character (Lingard, 2000), with states primarily funding public schools and the Commonwealth largely

funding private schools (Keating et al., 2012), each level maintaining significant autonomy. This dual system, with its inherent tensions between needs-based and entitlement-based funding, has shaped the unique landscape of Australian education.

As part of the Rudd-Gillard government's Education Revolution, The Gonski Review (2011) represented a pivotal moment, advocating for a needs-based approach through the Schooling Resource Standard (SRS)¹. However, implementation became fraught with political compromises, as vested interests and competing agendas often overshadowed the broader goal of equitable funding (Di Gregorio, 2023). As Connors and McMorrow (2015) highlight, political manoeuvring and prioritisation of private schooling have subsequently hindered funding equity progress. Despite reform efforts, recent reports such as Lamb (2020) and O'Brien (2023) continue to expose disparities in educational outcomes. These disparities underscore the need to move beyond simply critiquing the shortcomings of Australian school funding and towards identifying concrete pathways for reform.

Education Policy in Australia: complexities of federalism

Contemporary education policy in Australia as an interplay of federal and state responsibilities, represents more than just a set of legislative frameworks and funding mechanisms. From a critical policy analysis perspective, it embodies a contested terrain where power dynamics, ideological struggles, and socio-economic factors shape the very nature of educational access, opportunity, and outcomes (Ball, 1994).

While the Australian Constitution by default designates education as primarily a state responsibility (Birch, 1975), the federal government plays an increasingly significant role in funding and setting national agendas (Di Gregori, 2023). This dual governance structure creates a dynamic often fraught with negotiation and conflict (Savage, 2016). Federal involvement manifests through increasing investment and a national 'architecture' of statutory authorities that oversee national curriculum development,

¹ The Schooling Resource Standard (SRS) is a benchmark funding model introduced in the Gonski Review (2011) to ensure schools receive adequate resources to meet the educational needs of all students. It calculates a base level of funding per student, with additional loadings for disadvantage, including factors like socio-economic status, disability, Indigenous background, and school location. It is explained in more detail further on.

national reporting and standardised assessment programs (ACARA, n.d.), teacher standards (AITSL, n.d.), education research programs (AERO, n.d.) and agreements tied to performance indicators in exchange for federal funding (ACER, 2018). While intended to promote national consistency and address inequities, this approach can also lead to tensions between federal directives and state-specific priorities, creating challenges in policy implementation and potentially exacerbating existing disparities.

Critically examining education policy necessitates moving beyond a positivist understanding of policy as a linear formulation, implementation, and evaluation (Bacchi, 2009). Instead, a critical lens highlights the role of power relations and dominant discourses in shaping policy agendas as “a fundamentally political process: it involves major trade-offs between values” (Rizvi & Lingard, 2010 p. 72). For instance, the emphasis on standardised testing and performance-based accountability, prevalent in recent Australian education policy, reflects a neoliberal ideology that prioritises measurable outcomes and market-driven competition (Connell, 2013). While arguably promoting accountability, this focus can also narrow the curriculum, marginalise certain forms of knowledge, and exacerbate inequities between schools and student populations.

Education policy enactments involve a complex interplay of actors, including policymakers, educators, administrators, students, parents, and community and sectoral interest groups (Sinclair & Brooks, 2022). Policy texts, while providing a framework, are not deterministic. Their interpretation and implementation are mediated by these diverse actors, each with their interests, values, and understandings of the policy's intent; “they are... essentially contested in and between the arenas of formation and 'implementation” (Bowe, Ball, & Gold, 2017, p. 13). This process of translation and enactment can lead to unintended consequences, policy resistance, or even outright subversion of the original policy goals.

The impact of education policy varies across different social groups. Socioeconomic status, geographic location, Indigenous status, and disability can significantly influence how policy is experienced and its ultimate effects on educational outcomes (Thomson, 2002). Critical analysis requires attention to these differential impacts and understanding how policy can perpetuate or exacerbate existing inequalities. For

instance, funding models that allocate resources based on student performance can disadvantage schools in low socioeconomic areas, further entrenching existing disparities (OECD, 2021).

The Alice Springs (Mparntwe) Declaration

This Declaration, endorsed by Australian Education Ministers in December 2019, serves as a roadmap for the future of Australian education, continuing efforts toward more nationally consistent approaches to education policy (Savage et al., 2014). Building upon previous national declarations from Hobart, Adelaide and Melbourne, its stated purpose is to establish a shared “vision for education in Australia and commitment to improving educational outcomes for young Australians” (Mparntwe p. 3).

The declaration focuses on two interconnected goals:

1. **Excellence and Equity:** The Australian education system should promote excellence and equity, providing all young people access to high-quality, inclusive education free from discrimination.
2. **Youth Development:** All young Australians should become confident and creative individuals, successful lifelong learners, and active and informed community members.

A core element of the first goal is the explicit commitment to educational equity within the national framework. This commitment translates into a focus on recognising individual needs, identifying and addressing barriers to learning, and promoting personalised support tailored to individual capabilities (Bonnor et al., 2022). The declaration posits that educational equity requires equal access, targeted interventions, and individualised support to overcome systemic disadvantages, ensuring all young Australians can achieve their full educational potential regardless of background. This focus on educational equity is integral to the declaration's overarching vision for an inclusive and high-performing education system prepared to meet the challenges and opportunities of the future through a nationally consistent and collaborative approach.

Defining Equity in Education

While the concept of equity in education is often used interchangeably with equality, a distinction must be made. Equality typically focuses on providing the same resources or opportunities to all. At the same time, equity recognises that different students have different needs, and that fairness requires addressing these imbalances to ensure comparable outcomes (Espinoza, 2008). The OECD (2024) reinforces this distinction, highlighting equality of opportunity as a core principle, aiming to give all students equal chances to succeed regardless of their background. This approach often centres on inputs, such as access to resources and quality teaching.

Several scholars and policy documents offer perspectives on equity that build on input-focused equality of opportunity. For example, the Gonski Review (2011) describes the importance of resourcing schools to enable all students to "participate in the workforce and lead successful lives", implicitly linking equity to a threshold of educational attainment. This is reminiscent of the concept of "adequacy", as articulated by Gutmann (1987) and Koski & Reich (2007), which emphasises a minimum level of education necessary for individual and societal well-being. Sahlberg & Cobbold (2021) further refine this notion, defining adequate education as enabling full participation in adult society, referencing the OECD's (2019c) PISA Level 2 proficiency as a minimum benchmark.

Discussions of equity often incorporate a social justice dimension (Hyttens & Bettez, 2011), focusing on eliminating disparities in educational outcomes arising from socioeconomic status, Indigeneity, geographical location, and other factors. This perspective is evident in the Gonski Review (2011), which explicitly states that differences in student outcomes should not be a product of differences in wealth, income, power, or possessions. Similarly, Sahlberg & Cobbold (2021) advocate for similar average outcomes and a comparable range of outcomes across social groups.

This research adopts the Mparntwe Declaration's definition of equity as its foundation, recognising the interconnectedness of individual needs and systemic factors. Equity, therefore, is understood as ensuring all young Australians have access to high-quality education and are supported to reach their full potential, regardless of background or need. This perspective acknowledges that equity is not merely about

providing identical (equal) resources but creating a system that recognises and addresses diverse needs to ensure that all students have a genuine opportunity to succeed. This overarching 2nd Mparntwe goal is an authoritative declared benchmark against which current policies and practices can be evaluated.

Needs-Based Funding and the Schooling Resource Standard

The principle of needs-based funding in Australian education refers to a system where schools receive government funding based on the actual costs of educating their students, considering both individual student needs and school circumstances that drive additional costs (Gonski et al., 2011). The foundations of needs-based funding were established in the 1973 Karmel Report, which argued that funding should be allocated based on need rather than sector or historical precedent (Karmel, 1973; Kenway, 2013). This represented a significant shift from previous approaches focused on maintaining existing funding patterns between government and non-government schools. The 2011 Gonski Review reinforced and modernised this concept, recommending a needs-based funding model centred on a Schooling Resource Standard (SRS) with additional loadings for disadvantage, as explained in more detail below (Gonski et al., 2011). This model aimed to ensure that "differences in educational outcomes are not the result of differences in wealth, income, power or possessions" (Gonski et al., 2011, p. 105).

The Schooling Resource Standard (SRS) estimates the public funding a school needs to meet its students' educational needs. Calculated annually by the Commonwealth Department of Education, it comprises a base amount linked to student enrolment and indexed yearly, as well as needs-based loadings (Department of Education, 2023). Loadings address specific student needs (e.g., disability, Indigenous background, socio-educational disadvantage) and school characteristics (size, location). The SRS informs recurrent funding from the Australian Government, contributing at least 20% for government schools and 80% for non-government schools (though parental capacity to contribute is a factor reducing the base amount). State and territory funding contributions are also described using the SRS.

Despite the SRS framework outlining funding responsibilities for both federal and state/territory governments, a significant gap remains between projected funding contributions and actual amounts provided. With the exception of the Australian Capital Territory, no state or territory has consistently met

its target contributions towards achieving full SRS funding for all schools (Commonwealth Parliament, 2024; Dhir, 2024). This shortfall in state and territory contributions undermines the intended impact of the SRS and further exacerbates existing inequities (Rorris, 2021). This persistent underfunding raises questions about the political will and capacity to deliver on the equity goals articulated in the Mparntwe Declaration (Education Council, 2019).

The SRS base amount is determined by analysing the resources used by reference schools - those that achieve strong educational outcomes over sustained periods (ACARA, 2023). These schools must have at least 80% of students achieving above the national minimum standard in both reading and numeracy across three years of NAPLAN testing (Gonski et al., 2011). The loadings are calculated as percentages of the base amount, varying according to the level and concentration of disadvantage. For example, the low socioeconomic status loading ranges from 10% for schools with low concentrations to 50% for schools with high concentrations of disadvantaged students (Department of Education, 2023).

While the theory of needs-based funding is widely accepted, implementation has faced several challenges. Accurately measuring student need and disadvantage requires comprehensive, consistent data collection across all education sectors (Sahlberg & Cobbold, 2021). Furthermore, political resistance from stakeholders opposed to changes to historical funding patterns that would redistribute resources based on need has arisen (Reid, 2020). Finally, full implementation of needs-based funding requires significant investment from governments in a competitive fiscal environment (Bonnor et al., 2022).

The Australian Education Act 2013 legislates needs-based funding through the SRS model with oversight by the National School Resourcing Board (Department of Education, 2024). However, full implementation remains a work in progress. The Better and Fairer Schools Agreement 2025-2034 (Department of Education, 2024) seeks to accelerate progress toward full SRS funding for all schools. Challenges persist in overcoming political resistance (Dhir, 2024) and securing the necessary fiscal resources in the context of bilateral funding agreements between the Commonwealth and state and territory governments. In the Senate Enquiry of November 2024 into the Better Fairer Schools (Funding and Reform) Bill 2024 (Commonwealth Parliament, 2024) multiple submissions were made suggesting

that the bill falls short of the 100% funding targets (Australian Association for Research in Education, 2024), and that “Australia’s education system is being hampered by consistent underfunding of public schools relative to minimum agreed benchmarks” (Center for Future Work, 2024, p. 9). Other submissions also posited that to achieve genuine equity, education systems must improve data collection and analysis, increase transparency in funding decisions (Ellwood, 2024), strengthen accountability measures, and maintain consistent political will across electoral cycles (Australian Secondary Principals’ Association, 2024). Additional investment must also be strategically directed to areas with the greatest need (Sahlberg & Cobbold, 2021), which may be vulnerable to the calculus of political prioritisation.

Education Equity and Performance

Examining the relationship between equity and performance and the increasing segregation and socio-economic disparity in Australia establishes the empirical reality of inequity and its impact on student outcomes. It provides context for understanding how Australian school funding and regulation characteristics contribute to the misalignment between equity goals and outcomes.

The relationship between educational equity and system performance has been extensively documented through international research. Studies consistently demonstrate that education systems prioritising equity achieve superior overall outcomes. The OECD's (2019) analysis of PISA results reveals that high-performing education systems successfully combine quality with equity. Meanwhile, UNICEF's (2018) comprehensive review found that countries with more equitable education funding demonstrate smaller achievement gaps between advantaged and disadvantaged pupils.

Schleicher's (2020) examination of global education systems highlights that the most successful frameworks allocate resources equitably across schools, regardless of socioeconomic contexts. This finding is particularly pertinent when examining the Australian context, where school segregation and socioeconomic (SES) disparities present significant challenges to achieving equitable outcomes (Kenway, 2013).

Directions for Policy Reform

There appears to be scant appetite to consider long term, universally structural education policy reform for the Australian Federation, perhaps given the history of ideological and political contestation. Sinclair and Savage (2024) propose a new funding settlement for Australian schools, emphasising depoliticisation, longer funding cycles, policy action to dismantle structural inequalities, and increased transparency and accountability. Similarly, the Australian Learning Lecture's "Choice and Fairness" model conceived by Tom Greenwell and Chris Bonnor (Australian Learning Lecture, n.d.; Greenwell & Bonnor, 2022) champions a common framework, eliminating fees and mandating open enrolment in all publicly funded schools in exchange for full public funding. While sharing the goal of arms-length funding, the proposals differ in scope. Sinclair and Savage (2024) advocate for broader systemic reform, addressing historical disparities and promoting evidence-based policymaking, whereas the "Choice and Fairness" (2022) approach focuses primarily on regulatory reform and consistent, needs-based funding across sectors to create a level playing field for competition based on quality. Both ultimately aim to achieve greater equity through distinct funding and regulatory reforms, the focus of this analysis. Given the evidence of increasing inequity, despite the intent of Mparntwe (2019) and the international examples of successful equity policies, Australia must critically evaluate our own efforts and commit to a more ambitious policy dialogue.

Methodology

This chapter outlines the methods taken to investigate the key characteristics of the Australian school funding and regulatory environment as embodied in the 2024 Better Fairer Schools Agreement (BFSA) and how these characteristics contribute to the persistent misalignment between the equity goals articulated in the Mparntwe Declaration and educational outcomes. As a line of analysis, this research employs critical policy analysis (CPA), specifically utilising Carol Bacchi's (2009) "What's the Problem Represented to be?" (WPR) framework in order to examine the BFSA. This analysis is timely as the BFSA guides national education reform priorities for the next decade. It represents the latest blueprint for guiding national progress toward achievement of the goals as stated in the Mparntwe Declaration (2019).

This analysis will also draw upon other sources such as regulatory documents, and relevant parliamentary debates/inquiries since the 2019 Mparntwe statement.

The chapter is structured as follows: First, the theoretical underpinnings of critical policy analysis are discussed, situating Bacchi's WPR framework within this broader methodological approach. Second, the data sources used in this research are described, including specific policy documents and other relevant materials. The selection criteria for these sources are also explained, highlighting their relevance to the research question. Third, the analytical methods employed are detailed, outlining the application of Bacchi's six questions to the selected data. This section explains how the framework is used to unpack the problem representations embedded within Australian school funding and regulatory policies. Fourth, my positionality is addressed, acknowledging the potential influence of personal experience and perspective on the research process.

Theoretical Framework: Critical Policy Analysis

Critical policy analysis (CPA) moves beyond simply describing policy content to examine the underlying assumptions, power dynamics, and social contexts that shape policy formation and implementation (Ozga, 2000). It is a methodology that interrogates the nature of the “problem” a policy purports to address. Rather than accepting the problem as a given, CPA explores how problems are constructed and represented within policy discourse, recognising that these representations have significant implications for how issues are understood and addressed (Bacchi, 2009). This research adopts CPA as its guiding methodology, specifically utilising Carol Bacchi's (2012) "What's the Problem Represented to be?" (WPR) framework.

Bacchi's (2012) WPR framework provides a structured approach to deconstructing policy texts and practices by posing six key questions:

1. What's the “problem” represented to be?
2. What presuppositions or assumptions underlie this representation of the “problem”?
3. How has this representation of the “problem” come about?

4. What is left unproblematic in this problem representation? Where are the silences? Can the "problem" be thought about differently?
5. What effects are produced by this representation of the "problem"?
6. How/where has this representation of the "problem" been produced, disseminated, and defended?

Applying Bacchi's (2012) questions, the analysis can explore the deeper assumptions underpinning policy choices. It can enable consideration of what important influences and factors might be missing in the design of policy. The WPR approach allows for examining how particular problem representations privilege specific solutions while marginalising others (Stacey & Mockler et al. 2024), shedding light on the political and ideological forces shaping school funding and regulatory policies.

Critical policy analysis, and specifically the application of problem representation analysis, is widely used for examining public policy (Riemann, 2023). For example, Rizvi and Lingard (2010) critically examined the "global education reform movement" (GERM), questioning the dominant problem representation of declining educational standards and its influence on policies promoting standardised testing and accountability. Their analysis highlights how such problem representations can narrow curricula and exacerbate inequalities. Similarly, Savage and O'Connor (2014) analysed national curriculum reforms in Australia and the USA, deconstructing the problem representation of fragmentation and a need for national consistency. They demonstrated how this discourse centralises curriculum control while marginalising local contexts, reflecting the power dynamics and ideological struggles inherent in policy-making.

Epistemologically, critical policy analysis (CPA) aligns with a constructivist perspective. This perspective emphasises that knowledge and understanding are not objectively given but are socially constructed through discourse (Berger & Luckmann, 1966). Language, power dynamics, and social interactions shape our understanding of the world, including identifying and defining policy "problems" (Foucault, 1980). The WPR framework explicitly recognises this by focusing on how problems are represented within policy discourse. It acknowledges that policy is not a neutral instrument for addressing pre-existing issues but rather a product of power relations and dominant ideologies (Ball, 1994).

Ontologically, CPA aligns with perspectives that acknowledge the complex and contested nature of social reality (Colebatch, 2009). It recognises that "problems" are not objective entities existing independently of human interpretation but are shaped by the discourses surrounding them (Bacchi, 2009). By focusing on the discursive construction of problems, CPA provides a tool for understanding how policy shapes and is shaped by the social world, revealing the underlying assumptions, power dynamics, and ideological struggles in the policy process. This approach helps to denaturalise policy problems, allowing researchers to understand how certain issues become defined as problems needing policy intervention while others remain unaddressed (Bacchi & Goodwin, 2016).

Data Sources and Selection

The analysis focuses primarily on the Better and Fairer Schools Funding Agreement 2025-2034 (2024), as it represents the current agreement on school funding between the Commonwealth, states and territories.

The BFSFA represents a pivotal framework for shaping the funding and regulatory landscape of Australian schooling over the next decade. It is important to analyse the BFSFA as it seeks to operationalise the equity and excellence goals outlined in the Mparntwe Declaration, particularly through its focus on needs-based funding and systemic reforms. The agreement's provisions, including its commitment to addressing funding shortfalls in public schools and its emphasis on priority equity cohorts, have the potential to significantly influence educational outcomes across diverse contexts. By critically examining the BFSFA, this research can illuminate the alignment—or misalignment—between its stated objectives and the realities of its implementation, contributing to a deeper understanding of how policy mechanisms shape educational equity in Australia.

To date, not all the Bilateral Agreements associated with the Better and Fairer Schools Agreement 2025-2034 (BFSFA) have been finalised or published in the current Heads of Agreement. As a result, these jurisdiction-specific commitments have been omitted from this analysis. However, the Bilateral Agreements are critical for understanding how national objectives are adapted and implemented at the state and territory level, and their inclusion in a more comprehensive future analysis will be essential to fully assess the BFSFA's impact on educational equity and funding outcomes.

My analysis of the BFSA draws upon key elements within the agreement serving as primary data sources for examining its implications on educational equity and funding mechanisms.

Table 1. Elements of the BFSA used as data sources in this analysis

BFSA Element	Data Contribution
National Reform Directions (Part 4)	Outlines the specific areas of action, such as equity and excellence, wellbeing for learning, and workforce sustainability. These provide a basis for analysing policy priorities and their alignment with equity goals.
National Enabling Initiatives (Part 4 & Schedule B)	Details specific collaborative activities, such as the review of the Schooling Resource Standard (SRS) and the implementation of a Unique Student Identifier. These initiatives highlight the operational mechanisms of reform.
Funding Arrangements (Part 3)	Specifies the financial commitments of the Commonwealth and states/territories, including the path to achieving 100% of the SRS for public schools. These figures are analysed to assess funding adequacy and equity.
Improvement Measures (Part 2)	Defines the national targets and indicators for progress, such as Year 12 certification rates, learning proficiency levels, and attendance rates. These measures provide benchmarks to evaluate the agreement’s effectiveness.
Reporting and Transparency Framework (Part 5)	Outlines accountability measures, including Annual Implementation Reports and public dashboards, which are examined to assess the monitoring and evaluation of equity outcomes.

Secondary sources

This research also formatively draws on a range of Australian school funding policies, regulatory documents, and relevant parliamentary debates/inquiries from December 2019 onwards, coinciding with

the endorsement of the Mparntwe Declaration. This timeframe allows for examining the “persistent misalignment” between the Declaration's equity goals and educational outcomes, as highlighted in the research question. Examining policy developments after the Declaration provides insights into how its aspirations have been translated (or not) into concrete policy actions and their effects on equity in Australian education, and provide a contextual background for the BFSA as these inputs undoubtedly informed its development.

Table 2. Policy documents that are used to support the analysis of the Better and Fairer Schools

Policy Document	Date	Relevance to Research Question
Alice Springs (Mparntwe) Education Declaration	2019	Establishes the equity goals against which subsequent policies are evaluated. (One document)
The Schooling Resource Standard Documentation	Ongoing	Details the methodology for calculating the SRS, including loadings for student needs and school characteristics. (One Document)
Better and Fairer Schools (Funding and Reform) Bill 2024 [Provisions]	2024	Reflects the legislative attempt to enact the Better and Fairer Schools Agreement 2025-2034. 4 submissions related to this Bill are reviewed to understand a sampling of perspectives and arguments surrounding the proposed funding reforms. 4 documents in total (ACER, ASPA, Centre For Future Work, ACSSO)

Seven documents were included within the secondary data corpus. These documents were selected based on their direct relevance to the research question. The selection prioritises documents that articulate

policy goals, outline funding mechanisms, and reflect the perspectives of various stakeholders involved in the policy process.

This data will be analysed by considering and including grey literature, including media releases, reports from think-tanks... research acknowledges consideration of “soft influences” in my research (citation?). These include policy pronouncements by government officials, media releases, reports from think tanks and advocacy groups (e.g., the Gonski Institute, Save Our Schools), and public commentary on school funding. While these sources do not hold the same formal weight as legislation or official agreements, they are crucial for understanding the broader discursive context within which policy is formulated and implemented. From a CPA perspective, these “soft influences” contribute to the construction and dissemination of problem representations, shaping public understanding of issues and influencing the policy agenda (Bacchi, 2009). For example, media representations of school funding debates can frame the “problem” in particular ways, emphasising certain aspects while downplaying others. Similarly, advocacy group reports can contribute to specific problem representations that align with their interests and objectives. By noting these “soft influences” alongside formal policy documents, this research aims to provide a more nuanced understanding of the factors contributing to the persistent equity challenges in Australian education.

Analytical Methods

The six questions of Bacchi's (2009) "What's the Problem Represented to be?" (WPR) framework is systematically applied in this research to the selected data sources as follows.

1. What's the “problem” (of school funding and regulation) represented to be? This question focuses on identifying the specific problems that policies claim to address. Identifying the dominant problem representation is crucial for understanding the BFSA's underlying logic and intended effects.
2. What presuppositions or assumptions underlie this representation of the “problem”? This question explores unspoken assumptions that shape how the problem is understood. For example, a policy that focuses on funding disparities might assume that increased funding automatically translates

into improved outcomes, neglecting other factors like teacher quality or student socioeconomic background.

3. How has this representation of the “problem” come about? This question goes to the historical and social context that has given rise to the dominant problem representation that underpins the BFSAs. It considers the influence of various actors, discourses, and events in shaping how the problem is understood. Previous reference in this work to the historical evolution of school funding, from the Karmel Report (Karmel, 1973) to the Gonski Review (Gonski et al., 2011), provides a background to the development of different problem representations and the factors that have influenced their prominence.
4. What is left unproblematic in this problem representation? Where are the silences? Can the “problem” be thought about differently? This question encourages critical reflection on what aspects of the issue are overlooked or ignored in the dominant problem representation. This question can be applied to the secondary sources used in this research to identify alternative problem representations and perspectives that may be marginalised in the dominant policy discourse.
5. What effects are produced by this representation of the “problem”? This question examines the consequences of the dominant problem representation, both intended and unintended. For example, a policy that frames the problem as a lack of parental choice might lead to the expansion of school choice policies, potentially exacerbating school segregation and socioeconomic disparities (Bonnor & Shepherd, 2016). Analysing the impact of school funding policies on different school sectors and student populations might help identify the effects of particular problem representations on equity outcomes.
6. How/where has this representation of the “problem” been produced, disseminated, and defended? This question explores the mechanisms through which the dominant problem representation gains traction and becomes accepted as “truth”. It considers the role of various actors, institutions, and discourses in shaping public understanding of the issue. For example, media representations of

school funding debates can reinforce particular problem representations, influencing public opinion and policy decisions.

Researcher Positionality and Reflexivity

My position within the Australian education policy landscape significantly shapes this research. As an advocate for principals, I have been involved in policy formulation, advocacy, and stakeholder engagement for several years, working closely with government officials, educators, and community organisations. This experience gives me an “insider” perspective on the complexities of education policymaking. I acknowledge that this positionality influences my interpretations of policy and the research process itself.

My involvement in the policy process has given me first-hand experience of how problems are framed, debated, and ultimately addressed (or ignored) within the policy arena. I have witnessed how certain problem representations gain traction while others are marginalised and how these representations shape the range of possible policy solutions as “the outcome of the endless competition between ideas, interests and ideologies that impels our political system” (Althaus et al., 2023, p.1). This insider perspective informs my analysis of problem representations within school funding and regulatory policies. For example, my understanding of the political context surrounding the Gonski reviews and subsequent funding reforms allows me to examine the assumptions and motivations underlying different policy approaches critically. Furthermore, my experience working with diverse stakeholders, including those from disadvantaged communities, provides me with insights into the real-world impacts of funding policies on different student populations.

However, I also recognise that my positionality can introduce potential biases. My prior involvement in advocating for specific policy positions might predispose me to certain interpretations of the data. To mitigate these biases, I am committed to a reflexive research approach. As Pillow (2003) argues, reflexivity is not simply about acknowledging one’s position but actively interrogating how it shapes the

research process and findings. It involves an ongoing process of critical self-analysis that occurs throughout the research process (Pillow, 2003, p. 177). Following Pillow's insights, noting my assumptions, biases, and interpretations as they emerge during the research process helps me to remain aware of how my own perspectives might be influencing the analysis and to ensure that my interpretations are grounded in the data rather than pre-existing assumptions.

Furthermore, engaging with critical policy sociology literature, particularly the work of Ozga (2000), helps me to critically examine the power dynamics and social contexts that shape my own positionality and the policy landscape more broadly. Ozga's (2000) emphasis on the contested nature of policy knowledge and the influence of different actors and interests resonates with my own experiences in the policy arena. This theoretical lens helps me to analyse the data not just through my own insider perspective but also through a broader critical lens, considering the structural factors that shape policy decisions and their impact on equity.

My role as an advocate can also be understood in terms of "knowledge brokering". As a knowledge broker, I translate research findings, policy developments, and stakeholder perspectives to different audiences, facilitating communication and understanding between various actors in the policy process (Lomas, 2007). This research itself contributes to knowledge brokering by providing a critical analysis of school funding policies and their implications for equity. By disseminating the findings of this research through publications, presentations, and policy discussions, I aim to contribute to a deeper understanding of the challenges and opportunities in achieving equitable school funding in Australia. This research is not simply an academic exercise but a contribution to the ongoing policy debate, informing advocacy efforts and potentially influencing future policy decisions. By explicitly acknowledging and reflecting upon my positionality and role as a knowledge broker, I aim to enhance the transparency and rigour of this research, contributing to a more nuanced and informed understanding of Australian education policy.

Data Analysis

The Better and Fairer Schools Agreement 2025-2034 establishes the policy framework guiding the allocation of school funding and national education reform in Australia over the next decade. Structured across five key parts and accompanied by detailed schedules, it outlines the responsibilities of the Commonwealth, states, territories, and the non-government sector.

Part 1 addresses the roles, responsibilities, enforceability, and dispute resolution mechanisms for all parties. Part 2 articulates the purpose, objectives, and outcomes of the agreement, focusing on equity, excellence, student wellbeing, and workforce sustainability, alongside measurable improvement targets. Part 3 specifies funding arrangements, including the Commonwealth's commitment to increasing its contributions to government schools under the Schooling Resource Standard (SRS). Part 4 details national reform priorities, such as early intervention, wellbeing initiatives, and workforce attraction and retention strategies, while Part 5 introduces reporting and transparency mechanisms to ensure accountability.

The Agreement also includes schedules that guide bilateral implementation, cost-sharing principles, and annual performance reporting, reflecting its alignment with the equity goals of the Mparntwe Declaration.

Presented in subsections framed through the six questions of Bacci's WPR framework, the following Analysis and Discussion sections investigate how this important policy blueprint might address, or contribute to the persistent misalignment between the equity goals articulated in the Mparntwe Declaration and the realities of educational outcomes.

Subsection 1: What is the "problem" represented to be?

The BFSA (2024) frames the problem as inequitable resource distribution and public school underfunding. This representation is operationalised through the SRS, which is central to the agreement's funding arrangements. The SRS allocates base funding plus loadings for socio-educational disadvantage,

remoteness, and disability. By embedding these loadings, the BFSA (2024) attempts to ensure that resources are targeted to address the needs of the most disadvantaged students and communities.

The BFSA (2024) commits the Commonwealth to increase its share of the SRS for public schools from 20% to up to 25% by 2034, contingent on states and territories contributing at least 75% and eliminating indirect expenditures from their SRS share (Department of Education, 2024). This funding arrangement reflects the BFSA's interpretation of equity as fairness in resource allocation, consistent with the goals of the Mparntwe Declaration, which emphasises addressing barriers to learning and providing personalised support to enable all students to achieve their potential (Education Council, 2019).

This reflects the Gonski Review (2011), which argued funding disparities should not determine outcomes. By positioning needs-based funding as the primary policy mechanism, the BFSA builds on this legacy, presenting financial redistribution as the central solution to inequity.

The BFSA's (2024) "Enabling Initiatives" further reinforce the framing of equity as a funding issue by operationalising mechanisms to enhance the effectiveness of needs-based funding. For instance, the planned review of the SRS (BFSA 2024 p. 37) could potentially improve the accuracy of funding methodologies by addressing gaps in data collection or refining the calculation of loadings for disadvantage. Similarly, the implementation of a Unique Student Identifier (BFSA 2024, p. 22) may allow for better tracking of individual student progress across jurisdictions, strengthening accountability and transparency in resource allocation.

Subsection 2: What presuppositions or assumptions underlie this representation?

The BFSA (2024) is shaped by a series of key assumptions about the causes of inequity in Australian education and the mechanisms required to address it. These assumptions reflect a policy framework that prioritises measurable inputs, such as funding redistribution, and relies on voluntary compliance and transparency to achieve equity goals. While these presuppositions align with the agreement's focus on needs-based funding, their narrow scope reveals significant limitations in addressing the complex and systemic nature of educational disadvantage.

Assumption 1: Funding as the Primary Solution to Inequity

The central assumption underpinning the BFSA is that inequities in educational outcomes stem primarily from inadequate funding and that financial redistribution, guided by the Schooling Resource Standard (SRS), is the most effective means of addressing disadvantage. The SRS methodology, with its additional loadings for socio-educational disadvantage, geographic remoteness, and disability, reflects an overarching belief that directing more resources to schools with higher needs will reduce disparities and improve outcomes for priority equity cohorts (Department of Education, 2023).

Assumption 2: Voluntary Compliance by States and Territories

Another implicit assumption of the BFSA (2024) is that states and territories will reliably meet their funding obligations and implement needs-based funding models in alignment with the agreement's goals. The reliance on Schedule D (BFSA p. 42), which will outline bilateral agreements with individual states and territories, reflects a belief in the effectiveness of voluntary compliance rather than enforceable mandates (Department of Education, 2024). This approach assumes that states and territories will prioritise education funding despite competing fiscal pressures and political constraints.

Assumption 3: Transparency as a Driver of Accountability

The BFSA (2024) assumes that transparency mechanisms, such as public reporting and annual implementation reviews, will ensure accountability and drive progress towards equity goals. Part 5 – Reporting and Public Transparency requires states and territories to publish detailed data on funding arrangements and compliance with the SRS (Department of Education, 2024). These measures aim to promote public confidence in the system and encourage stakeholders to fulfil their commitments.

Assumption 4: Equity as a Measurable and Financial Construct

The BFSA (2024) conceptualises equity primarily as a measurable construct tied to funding redistribution: "The Act sets out conditions on states and territories for grants of financial assistance based on the Schooling Resource Standard (SRS). The SRS is made up of a base funding amount for

every student plus additional loadings for schools and students with greater needs.” (BFSA 2024, Clause 14, p. 4). By centring its approach on the SRS and associated loadings, the agreement treats equity as a financial issue, where fairness is equated with resource allocation. This narrow definition assumes that educational disadvantage can be quantified and addressed purely through financial inputs, neglecting the broader cultural and systemic factors that perpetuate disparities.

The ‘Enabling Initiatives’ (p. 20.) outlined in the BFSA (2024) reinforce these assumptions by focusing on improving the technical aspects of funding distribution. For instance, the planned review of the SRS could enhance the accuracy of funding methodologies, while the implementation of a Unique Student Identifier may improve data tracking and transparency (Department of Education, 2024). These initiatives reflect the BFSA’s reliance on measurable, data-driven approaches to equity.

Subsection 3: How has this representation of the "problem" come about?

The representation of the "problem" in the BFSA as one of funding inequity is deeply rooted in the historical, political, and ideological evolution of Australian education policy. Over time, the discourse around equity has become closely tied to resource redistribution, shaped by pivotal policy milestones, the dynamics of federal governance, and the influence of neoliberal ideologies. This historical continuity has positioned funding as the central mechanism for addressing disparities in educational outcomes, while other systemic and structural considerations have been deprioritised.

Subsection 4: What is left unproblematic in this problem representation? Where are the silences?

The BFSA (2024) frames inequity in Australian education primarily as a funding shortfall, operationalised through the Schooling Resource Standard (SRS). While this representation draws attention to the critical issue of resource inadequacy, it leaves other aspects of inequity unexamined. Key structural, cultural, and systemic barriers remain unproblematised, reflecting significant silences in the BFSA’s approach. For example, socio-economic segregation between schools—driven by school choice policies, selective enrolment practices, and geographic inequalities—creates significant disparities in

student outcomes (Bonnor & Shepherd, 2016). These omissions limit the agreement's capacity to address the root causes of educational disadvantage and invite alternative ways of conceptualising the "problem."

The BFSA (2024) does not address operational reforms, such as the mandated assessment, curriculum and reporting requirements, industrial agreements, and school-level priorities that directly impact educational equity. The reliance on transparency and voluntary compliance by states and territories in the BFSA also leaves unproblematic the absence of enforceable accountability mechanisms.

Cultural and social dimensions of inequity are similarly absent from the BFSA's framing of the problem. For Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander students, educational disadvantage is shaped not only by resource inadequacy but also by systemic racism, cultural disconnection, and a lack of representation in curricula and teaching staff (Education Council, 2019). While the BFSA provides additional funding for Indigenous students through the SRS loadings, it does not propose initiatives to address these deeper cultural issues.

Subsection 5: What effects are produced by this representation of the "problem"?

The BFSA (2024) frames inequity in Australian education as a resource gap, which produces several significant effects, shaping policy priorities, governance practices, and the broader discourse on equity in education. While the BFSA's focus on funding highlights the importance of resource redistribution, it also incorporates accountability mechanisms, including links to standardised test results, which introduce a performance-based element into its equity framework². This dual focus reinforces existing inequities, limits systemic change, and narrows the scope of reform. For example, while resource redistribution aims to address funding gaps, the reliance on accountability measures tied to performance risks penalising underperforming schools that serve disadvantaged populations, further entrenching disparities.

Additionally, the BFSA does not address the ongoing sectoral inequities or the fragmentation of responsibility for delivering the Mparntwe goals, which persists through the bilateral agreements.

² Clause 67 of the BFSA (2024, p. 14) specifies that national Improvement Measures, such as proficiency levels in NAPLAN Reading and Numeracy, will be tracked to monitor progress. This approach, while aiming to drive equity through transparency, risks framing funding allocation in terms of student performance on standardised assessments.

Subsection 6: How/where has this representation of the "problem" been produced, disseminated, and defended?

The representation of inequity in the BFSA as a funding issue has been produced through policy mechanisms such as the Schooling Resource Standard (SRS) and its associated loadings. The SRS, as a central feature of the BFSA, operationalises the problem representation by quantifying funding needs and framing equity as a resource allocation issue (Department of Education, 2023). This problem framing is further legitimised by its alignment with recommendations from the Gonski Review (2011), which positioned needs-based funding as the primary mechanism for addressing disparities in educational outcomes.

The BFSA's problem representation has also been disseminated and defended through its reliance on bilateral agreements between the Commonwealth and state/territory governments (BFSA, Clauses 24–25, 87; Schedule D). These agreements allow for jurisdictional flexibility in implementing needs-based funding, reflecting the federal structure of Australian education governance (Department of Education, 2024). This flexibility reinforces the narrative that funding inequity can be addressed through cooperative federalism and voluntary compliance, rather than enforceable mandates.

Public reporting and transparency measures, outlined in Part 5 of the BFSA, serve as additional mechanisms for disseminating and defending the problem representation. By requiring states and territories to publish detailed data on funding arrangements and compliance with the SRS, these measures aim to promote accountability and build public confidence in the agreement's equity goals (Department of Education, 2024). Transparency is positioned as a key driver of progress, with mechanisms such as annual implementation reports and dashboards designed to monitor the alignment between funding commitments and equity outcomes.

The problem representation is further defended by the BFSA's (2024) focus on Enabling Initiatives (p. 20), such as the planned review of the SRS and the implementation of a Unique Student Identifier (BFSA, 2024, pp. 21, 34-35). These initiatives are framed as tools for improving the accuracy and accountability

of funding distribution, reinforcing the assumption that financial redistribution is the most effective solution to inequity (Department of Education, 2024). The emphasis on these technical improvements strengthens the legitimacy of the problem representation by presenting it as data-driven and evidence-based.

Advocacy groups, parliamentary inquiries, and think tanks have also played a role in producing and defending the BFSA's (2024) problem representation. For instance, submissions to the Senate Inquiry into the Better and Fairer Schools (Funding and Reform) Bill 2024 highlight the widespread acceptance of needs-based funding as a cornerstone of equity policy (Australian Association for Research in Education, 2024; Centre for Future Work, 2024).

Discussion

Limitations of the BFSA's Framing of Equity

Subsection 1: What's the problem represented to be?

While the BFSA (2024) addresses funding inequity, its framing is limited. The agreement overlooks broader structural and cultural barriers that contribute to inequities in Australian education. For example, entrenched socio-economic segregation and school choice policies exacerbate disparities by concentrating disadvantage in public schools, while private schools continue to benefit from significant public subsidies, perpetuating an unfair funding structure (Bonnor & Shepherd, 2016; Cobbold, 2019). These systemic issues are not addressed within the BFSA's framing of the problem.

The BFSA (2024) assumes that fair funding directly improves outcomes, as evidenced by its assertion that "adequate and fair funding is foundational to ensuring that every student, regardless of background, has access to the resources and opportunities needed to achieve educational success" (BFSA, 2024, p. 4). While adequate funding is essential for providing resources, infrastructure, and staffing, addressing inequities also requires tackling deeper cultural and systemic barriers, such as discriminatory practices, implicit biases, and the socio-economic stratification of schools (Connell, 2013; Ellwood, 2024). For

example, although the BFSA (2024) commits to reviewing the SRS methodology to ensure funding delivers "measurable improvements in learning outcomes" (BFSA, 2024, p. 21), this focus on financial inputs overlooks the complex challenges faced by marginalised groups. Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander students, for instance, face barriers rooted in systemic racism and cultural disconnection, which cannot be resolved through funding alone (Education Council, 2019). Similarly, students with disabilities often require costly systemic reforms to ensure inclusive practices, which extend beyond financial allocations (Sahlberg & Cobbold, 2021).

Subsection 2: What presuppositions or assumptions underlie this representation?

The assumption that inequities in educational outcomes stem primarily from inadequate funding is rooted in the broader policy discourse emphasising needs-based funding as a central mechanism for achieving equity, as articulated in the Gonski Review (2011). Research shows this relationship is more complex: while funding is necessary, it is insufficient on its own to address systemic barriers, such as teacher shortages in disadvantaged schools, socio-economic segregation, and cultural disconnection (Sahlberg & Cobbold, 2021). The BFSA (2024) seeks to challenge resource distribution inequities through specific initiatives, such as the commitment to "allocate at least 95% of the Schooling Resource Standard (SRS) to all schools by 2032" (BFSA, 2025, p. 12) and the review of the SRS base and loadings methodology to ensure needs-based funding "delivers measurable improvements in student outcomes" (BFSA, 2024, p. 21). While these initiatives aim to redistribute resources more equitably, the BFSA oversimplifies the multifaceted nature of educational disadvantage by assuming that funding alone can resolve challenges like socio-economic segregation and systemic inequities.

No state or territory—apart from the Australian Capital Territory—has consistently met its SRS funding targets for public schools (Rorris, 2021). Political variability, economic pressures, and competing policy priorities often lead to underinvestment in public schools, particularly those serving disadvantaged communities. The assumption that this will somehow be different over the course of three or four election cycles seems brave. By relying on voluntary compliance without enforceable penalties or incentives, the BFSA (2024) risks perpetuating inequities in funding distribution and undermining its equity agenda.

The agreement also overlooks the limitations of transparency as a sole accountability mechanism. While public reporting can highlight funding shortfalls and inequities, it does not compel states to rectify these issues. Historical evidence demonstrates that transparency measures alone have not prevented states from underfunding public schools or redirecting resources to other priorities (Ellwood, 2024). Without enforceable penalties or incentives for compliance, transparency risks becoming symbolic rather than substantive, failing to address the deeper structural barriers to equity.

While the BFSA provides additional funding for Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander students, it does not address deeper cultural barriers, such as systemic racism and the lack of culturally responsive teaching practices (Education Council, 2019). Similarly, while fair funding is a necessary starting point for addressing the challenges faced by students with disabilities, it must be accompanied by systemic reforms to ensure equitable access to specialist support services and inclusive pedagogical practices (Sahlberg & Cobbold, 2021). By presupposing that financial redistribution alone can achieve equity, the BFSA overlooks the need for targeted initiatives to address these non-financial dimensions of disadvantage.

Subsection 3: How has this representation of the "problem" come about?

The BFSA's (2024) reliance on bilateral agreements with states and territories reflects the political compromises needed to navigate Australia's complex education governance landscape. These agreements allow for jurisdictional flexibility in funding commitments, reflecting the challenges of achieving national consistency within a decentralised federal framework (Department of Education, 2024). The continued prioritisation of needs-based funding within this context represents a pragmatic response to these constraints but also highlights the limitations of relying on voluntary compliance to achieve equity goals.

The 'Enabling Initiatives' aim to improve the accuracy and transparency of funding distribution including tenuously proposed work to better understand socio-economic diversity and review the Measurement Framework for Schooling (BFSA 2024, p.37&38), aligning with the broader policy discourse on needs-

based funding. However, the focus on technical improvements rather than systemic reform highlights the continued dominance of financial redistribution as the preferred solution to inequity.

By focusing on measurable financial inputs, the BFSA (2024) agreement aligns with the neoliberal emphasis on data-driven interventions while neglecting systemic reforms to address socio-economic segregation, unequal access to quality teachers, and cultural barriers (Bonnor & Shepherd, 2016; Sahlberg & Cobbold, 2021). The BFSA's framing reflects this broader trend of prioritising efficiency and accountability over transformative change. This selective adoption illustrates how policy priorities are shaped by political and institutional constraints.

Subsection 4: What is left unproblematic in this problem representation? Where are the silences?

A loud silence in the agreement reflects the political sensitivity of addressing school segregation. While the BFSA prioritises increased funding for public schools—committing to "at least 95% of the SRS being provided to all public schools by 2032" (BFSA, 2025, p. 12)—it does little to challenge the structural inequities that underpin resource disparities. Private schools continue to benefit from substantial public subsidies alongside their capacity to generate significant private income (Bonnor & Shepherd, 2016; Cobbold, 2019). Yet, the agreement fails to impose enforceable conditions on private schools to align with equity goals, such as enrolling more disadvantaged students or adopting inclusive practices. It also does not propose reducing subsidies to overfunded private schools or addressing the inequities caused by their ability to supplement public funding with high private fees.

This omission perpetuates structural inequities by allowing private schools to disproportionately benefit from public subsidies without accountability for addressing systemic barriers like socio-economic segregation. To close this gap, enforceable mechanisms are essential, such as tying public funding to equity benchmarks, requiring transparent reporting on resource use, and imposing penalties for non-compliance. Without these measures, the BFSA risks entrenching existing inequities rather than addressing them.

Despite the contestable assertion at section 15 in the BFSFA (2024) that ‘the constitutional responsibility for school education lies with states and territories’ (p 5) it is hard to ignore the neglect of operational factors. The agreement’s narrow focus on resource redistribution overlooks how school operations—including curriculum priorities, and pedagogical approaches—shape educational outcomes and perpetuate disadvantage. This omission represents a significant limitation, as operational reforms are essential to addressing structural inequities and fostering inclusive learning environments.

The vague timelines and accountability mechanisms for the BFSFA’s ‘Enabling Initiatives’ highlight a significant disconnect between the agreement’s ambitious goals and its capacity to deliver tangible outcomes. Without enforceable deadlines or clear implementation plans, initiatives such as the review of the Measurement Framework for Schooling and the proposed work on socioeconomic diversity risk delays or indefinite postponement, undermining their credibility and impact.

The reliance on public reporting and bilateral agreements assumes that transparency will drive compliance, but this approach does not address the structural and political barriers that prevent states from prioritising public school funding. By leaving these accountability gaps unexamined, the BFSFA risks repeating the failures of previous agreements, perpetuating inequities in resource distribution.

To address these silences, the "problem" of inequity in Australian education must be reconceptualised as a multidimensional issue that extends beyond funding. By broadening its focus, the BFSFA could align more closely with the equity principles of the Mparntwe Declaration (2019), which emphasises addressing barriers to learning and ensuring personalised support for all students (Education Council, 2019).

Policy Implications and Recommendations

Subsection 5: What effects are produced by this representation of the "problem"?

Policies that contribute to socio-economic segregation—such as school choice and selective enrolment/de-enrolment practices—are left unchallenged in the BFSFA, despite their role in concentrating

disadvantage in under-resourced schools (Bonnor & Shepherd, 2016). Additionally, the BFSA's inclusion of accountability mechanisms tied to standardised test results complicates its equity narrative. Clause 67 specifies that 'the Parties agree to focus on measures that... promote a greater understanding of how the joint effort of governments, school systems, and approved authorities are leading to better outcomes for students and educators,' (BFSA 2024, p.14) including targets related to NAPLAN results. While transparency and measurable outcomes are important, such mechanisms risk penalising schools serving disadvantaged populations, reinforcing inequities rather than addressing them. This dual emphasis on both resource redistribution and performance accountability highlights a tension within the BFSA that narrows its potential for systemic reform.

By prioritising financial inputs over systemic change, the agreement tacitly condones the structural inequities that perpetuate disparities in student outcomes. For instance, the BFSA (2024) commits to increasing public school funding to "at least 95% of the Schooling Resource Standard (SRS) by 2032" (BFSA, 2024, p. 12) but does not propose enforceable measures to ensure that resources are directly targeted at addressing systemic barriers, such as socio-economic segregation or teacher shortages in disadvantaged schools. Similarly, the agreement dedicates significant resources to funding loadings for disadvantaged cohorts, such as Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander students or those with disabilities, without mandating the implementation of culturally responsive teaching, inclusive practices, or targeted reforms to address the unique challenges faced by these groups (BFSA, 2024, pp. 15–17).

The fragmented shared responsibility expected through the bilateral agreements with states and territories undermines the BFSA's capacity to achieve national consistency in equity outcomes. Instead of addressing inequities holistically, the agreement produces a patchwork of funding arrangements that will vary by jurisdiction and subsequently by sector, leaving disadvantaged schools in some regions more vulnerable to underfunding (BFSA, 2024, p. 4).

Further, the BFSA's focus on funding as a technical solution to inequity depoliticises the broader structural and cultural challenges that underpin educational disadvantage. Systemic issues such as socio-economic segregation, cultural exclusion, and inequitable access to high-quality teachers are sidelined in

favour of financial redistribution. This depoliticisation reinforces the status quo, limiting opportunities for transformative change.

The BFSA's narrow problem framing risks limiting its long-term impact on equity in Australian education. While increased funding for disadvantaged schools is critical, it is insufficient to address the root causes of educational inequity. Without addressing systemic barriers, SRS funding may not improve outcomes. To mitigate the effects of the narrow problem framing, Australian education policy must adopt a more comprehensive vision of equity.

Subsection 6: How/where has this representation of the "problem" been produced, disseminated, and defended?

While the BFSA's reliance on mechanisms such as the SRS and transparency measures reinforces its problem representation, these tools are limited in their capacity to address the deeper structural and systemic barriers to equity. By framing equity narrowly as a funding issue, the BFSA risks perpetuating a fragmented approach to reform.

The reliance on voluntary compliance through bilateral agreements undermines the BFSA's problem representation. While these agreements allow for jurisdictional flexibility, they also create inconsistencies in how funding and equity reforms are implemented across states and territories. Historical evidence demonstrates that voluntary compliance often results in underfunding for public schools, particularly in disadvantaged communities, as states prioritise other fiscal or political interests (Rorris, 2021). Without enforceable accountability mechanisms, the BFSA's equity goals remain vulnerable to political and economic variability.

Transparency measures, while valuable for monitoring and reporting, are insufficient as standalone accountability mechanisms. Public reporting does not compel states or territories to meet their SRS funding targets, nor does it address the systemic barriers that perpetuate inequities. The emphasis on transparency risks becoming performative, rather than substantive, if it is not accompanied by enforceable

penalties or incentives for non-compliance (Ellwood, 2024). This limitation weakens the BFSA's capacity to achieve meaningful progress toward equity.

The Enabling Initiatives, while framed as solutions to improve funding accuracy and accountability, lack firm timelines and measurable outcomes. The absence of enforceable deadlines raises questions about their impact and feasibility. This vagueness undermines the credibility of the initiatives, limiting their potential to drive meaningful reforms.

Advocacy and stakeholder engagement have played a critical role in shaping and defending the BFSA's problem representation, but these efforts have also revealed significant tensions. For example, submissions to the Senate Inquiry have called for greater transparency, stronger accountability measures, and increased investment in public schools (Australian Association for Research in Education, 2024; Centre for Future Work, 2024). These critiques highlight the limitations of the BFSA's narrow framing of equity and suggest a need for broader, enforceable approaches to reform.

To strengthen the BFSA's capacity to achieve equity, Australian education policy must move beyond the current problem representation and adopt an approach more likely to achieve the goals of Mparntwe (2019) over the longer term. This approach could include addressing the fundamental systemic conditions and drivers of inequity through introduction of common regulations and enforceable accountability mechanisms for all Australian Schools in receipt of public monies to ensure funding commitments are met.

Conclusion

The Better and Fairer Schools Agreement 2025-2034 (2024) addresses inequities by prioritising needs-based funding (on paper). This approach builds on the legacy of the Gonski Review (2011) and aligns with the equity goals articulated in the Mparntwe Declaration, which emphasises ensuring all students have access to high-quality education and the resources necessary to achieve their potential. However, the BFSA's narrow framing of inequity as primarily a funding issue leaves broader structural, operational, and cultural barriers unexamined, limiting its capacity to achieve meaningful and lasting equity in Australian education.

The agreement's reliance on the Schooling Resource Standard (SRS) as the central funding mechanism reflects a significant policy commitment to addressing the immediate resource gaps faced by disadvantaged schools and students. This focus is a necessary step in creating a more equitable education system, particularly for priority equity cohorts such as Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander students, students with disabilities, and those in rural and remote areas. However, while the SRS provides a framework for addressing funding disparities, the BFSA's implementation relies heavily on voluntary compliance by states and territories, without enforceable accountability mechanisms. This reliance on transparency and bilateral agreements assumes that states will prioritise public school funding, despite historical evidence of underfunding and competing fiscal priorities. As a result, the agreement risks perpetuating existing inequities rather than addressing them.

The BFSA's (2024) 'Enabling Initiatives' (p 7) offer potential improvements in the accuracy and accountability of funding mechanisms. However, the vague timelines and lack of enforceable deadlines for these initiatives undermine their credibility and feasibility. Without clear implementation plans and measurable outcomes, these initiatives risk becoming symbolic gestures rather than substantive reforms. This lack of urgency reflects a broader limitation within the BFSA, where ambitious policy objectives are not matched by concrete plans for execution, leaving critical operational and systemic barriers unaddressed.

The BFSA overlooks structural and cultural inequities. Socio-economic segregation, driven by school choice policies and selective enrolment practices, remains unchallenged within the agreement, despite its documented impact on concentrating disadvantage in under-resourced public schools (Cobbold, 2020; Sahlberg & Cobbold, 2021). For instance, while the agreement highlights funding as a mechanism for equity, it fails to address how these policies perpetuate inequities by enabling advantaged schools to selectively enrol students, leaving public schools to manage higher concentrations of disadvantage (BFSA, 2024, p. 8).

Addressing these gaps requires a more comprehensive approach. There is a pressing need to establish a fairer regulatory framework that levels the playing field for all students. This includes addressing systemic inequities such as socio-economic segregation, strengthening oversight of school funding distribution, and ensuring that public subsidies for private schools are tied to equity-focused benchmarks. Implementing enforceable accountability measures and fostering greater consistency across states and territories would help ensure that all students, regardless of background or school sector, have equitable access to quality education. By broadening our reform focus, Australian federated education policy could achieve a better alignment with the Mparntwe Declaration's (2019) vision of equity and excellence, addressing the structural and systemic root causes of educational inequity, and be more likely to deliver sustained improvements in outcomes for all Australian students.

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